

D1.4: Plan on Legacy

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ABSTRACT:	<p>The Plan on Legacy defines the long-term sustainability strategy for XR4HUMAN's key outputs, ensuring their continued relevance and accessibility beyond the project's lifetime. XR4Europe will assume responsibility for hosting and maintaining the Experience Library, Ratings Repository, and Forum, while NTUA will preserve the project website and Interoperability Guide for at least five years. The strategy includes the migration of dynamic web assets to XR4Europe's infrastructure, the positioning of the XR Code of Conduct as a living document, and the evolution of the Experience Library through academic partnerships, annual reviews, and an independent evaluation process. The Forum will be sustained as a multichannel, multimodal platform for ethical dialogue, complemented by semesterly workshops and outreach to new EU projects. Risk assessment and mitigation measures address financial, technological, and engagement challenges, with particular emphasis on integration with European strategic initiatives such as the Virtual Worlds Partnership and the Virtual Worlds Skills Academy. Together, these measures ensure that</p>
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	XR4HUMAN's outputs remain impactful resources for Europe's XR ecosystem, supporting the development of ethical, inclusive, and human-centred virtual worlds.
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Table of contents

1	Legacy Strategy and Roadmap	6
1.1	Migration and Maintenance of Web Assets	6
1.2	Continuation of the XR4HUMAN Forum	7
1.3	Sustainability of the Experience Library	7
1.4	Continuity of the Ratings Repository	8
1.5	Sustainability of the Interoperability Guide	8
2	Risk Assessment and Mitigation	9

1 Legacy Strategy and Roadmap

Task 1.5 was designed to define viable post-project paths for XR4HUMAN outputs. XR4Europe has taken the lead in ensuring sustainability by assuming responsibility for hosting, maintaining, and promoting core outputs such as the Experience Library, the Ratings Repository, and the Forum. NTUA will maintain the XR4HUMAN website and social media accounts for at least five years, preserving the project's digital presence. Together, these commitments provide the structural basis for ensuring that the project's resources remain publicly accessible and that they continue to influence policy, research, and industry practices in Europe.

1.1 Migration and Maintenance of Web Assets

A central element of XR4HUMAN's sustainability strategy is the migration of its dynamic web assets from NTUA servers to XR4Europe's own hosting infrastructure. This includes both the Experience Library and the Ratings Repository, the latter being the home of the living version of the XR Code of Conduct. Migration will ensure that XR4Europe has full administrative access to update, curate, and expand these resources, while the XR4HUMAN website maintained by NTUA will continue to serve as the central gateway for at least five years after the project's end.

The migration will preserve visual identity, functionality, and the public accessibility of these resources. URLs will redirect seamlessly from xr4human.eu to xr4europe.eu, ensuring continuity for users while maintaining XR4HUMAN branding. The Experience Library and Ratings Repository will remain publicly accessible and free of membership barriers. Migration is scheduled to be completed by January 2026, following a brief transitional period after the project's closure. This step secures the long-term sustainability of XR4HUMAN's most interactive and evolving outputs.

Key milestone: Completion of migration to XR4Europe hosting by January 2026.

1.2 Continuation of the XR4HUMAN Forum

The XR4HUMAN Forum, rebuilt on Discourse's managed hosting service in 2025, will be maintained by XR4Europe as a cornerstone of the project's legacy. By covering the hosting costs of approximately €100 per month, XR4Europe guarantees the Forum's operational stability for at least three years beyond the project period. A biannual evaluation process will assess its performance, activity levels, and cost-effectiveness, with the option to migrate to another platform should Discourse become unsuitable.

Beyond technical continuity, the Forum will evolve from a project-centric space into a broader European hub for ethical dialogue in XR and virtual worlds. XR4Europe will actively broaden the scope of discussions, introducing new topics related to accessibility, inclusivity, data security, algorithmic fairness, and human-centred design. This will transform the Forum into a resource not only for those familiar with XR4HUMAN but also for new stakeholders entering the field.

To sustain engagement, XR4Europe will launch a cycle of semesterly online workshops hosted within the Forum's webVR space hosted on Arrival.Space. These will be co-organised with partners such as XRSI Europe as well as with other EU-funded projects and national initiatives according to opportunity, who will bring complementary expertise and perspectives. For example, one workshop series will focus on accessibility standards, while another will examine best practices for protecting minors in immersive environments. Summaries and recommendations from these workshops will be published directly in the Forum, reinforcing its role as both a discussion space and a repository of insights.

The Forum will also serve as an outreach channel to new Horizon Europe projects, particularly those funded under HUMAN-14, HUMAN-15, and HUMAN-16 in the 2025 Work Programme, which must incorporate relevant human-centered design, data privacy, accessibility, and interoperability elements. XR4Europe will invite these projects to present their ethical approaches, share draft frameworks, and solicit feedback from Forum participants. In this way, the Forum will become a living platform for inter-project dialogue and peer learning.

Finally, XR4Europe will ensure the Forum's international visibility by continuing to present it at conferences, such as United XR, and standardisation workshops across Europe, inviting national XR associations and global partners to participate. In this context, XR4Europe will continue to build the Forum's position as a unique pan-European resource complementing global initiatives such as XRSI and the XR Guild.

KPI: Semesterly online workshops hosted in the Forum's Arrival.Space venue; biannual evaluation of activity and impact.

1.3 Sustainability of the Code of Conduct

The XR Code of Conduct represents one of XR4HUMAN's most visible and impactful outputs. XR4Europe will ensure its sustainability by positioning it as a living document, continuously updated in response to stakeholder feedback and evolving regulatory frameworks. Its public version will be hosted within the Ratings Repository, which will act as the definitive access point for the most recent edition. This will allow for transparent tracking of revisions and stakeholder contributions.

To ensure wide dissemination and uptake, XR4Europe will collaborate closely with the Virtual Worlds Partnership Association, created by Siemens and other founding partners. Through this collaboration, the Code will be disseminated to the Partnership's members via annual webinars and joint workshops. The first series of webinars is planned for Fall 2026, timed to coincide with the early periods of new Horizon Europe projects. This strategic timing maximises the likelihood that consortia beginning their work will adopt the Code of Conduct as a guiding framework. Future webinars will be pitched as joint efforts between XR4Europe and the Partnership, lending institutional weight and visibility to the dissemination effort.

In parallel, XR4Europe will actively present the Code of Conduct at conferences, policy roundtables, and standards-related working groups at national, European, and global levels. For example, presentations are foreseen at United XR, where XR4Europe will organise a dedicated session on ethics and human-centred design. At the policy level, XR4Europe will contribute to European Commission working groups and cross-sector ethical initiatives, ensuring alignment between the Code and broader EU digital policies.

At the global level, XR4Europe will begin to participate in the Metaverse Standards Forum to promote the Code as a European contribution to international standards. This engagement will also aim to include contributing case studies and recommendations derived from European projects adopting the Code. This is subject to such adoption and sharing of case studies.

KPI: At least two annual dissemination webinars in cooperation with the Virtual Worlds Partnership; regular updates to the living Code hosted in the Ratings Repository.

1.4 Sustainability of the Experience Library

The Experience Library will remain a vital platform for showcasing XR projects that exemplify ethical and human-centred design. Its sustainability will rely on both the technical migration to XR4Europe and proactive strategies to ensure continued contributions. The Library will be fully replicated on the XR4Europe website, maintaining its branding to preserve identity and recognition while aligning with XR4Europe's design framework. A direct link will remain accessible through the XR4HUMAN website to guarantee continuity for existing users.

Beyond technical continuity, XR4Europe has initiated discussions with universities, including St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (Austria) and Avans University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), to integrate the Library into curricula. This would allow student projects submitted as coursework or graduation work to be uploaded directly, ensuring a steady pipeline of new content and embedding the Library into the European education ecosystem.

To maintain the integrity and value of the Library, the application evaluation process will evolve from the approach piloted during XR4HUMAN. A volunteer-based pool of evaluators, coordinated by Professor Oliver Schreer (XR4Europe Board of Directors, WP6 co-lead), will oversee methodological consistency, quality assurance, and recruitment of additional contributors. This evaluation pool will include experts from the XR4HUMAN network, XR4Europe's membership, and external collaborators. Evaluations will not be a static continuation of the earlier process, but will continue to adapt, drawing on the ethical self-assessments and progressively integrating the project's final outputs, including the XR Code of Conduct, the Interoperability Guide, and the ethical self-assessment checklist. This ensures that evaluations remain robust, credible, and responsive to the evolving ethical and technical landscape of XR.

An annual review cycle will be established after the conclusion of XR4HUMAN to ensure that the Library adapts to emerging trends and community needs. These reviews will be conducted online and will involve representatives from XR4HUMAN partners, the evaluator pool, and XR4Europe's management team. The annual review will cover multiple dimensions:

- **Scope and relevance:** assessing whether the categories of projects featured remain aligned with developments in the XR ecosystem, and determining whether adjustments are needed (e.g., extending eligibility to more commercial projects).
- **Application and evaluation process:** examining the efficiency, clarity, and fairness of submission workflows, incorporating feedback from evaluators and applicants, and updating criteria in line with the latest ethical standards and interoperability practices.
- **Communication and visibility:** evaluating how effectively the Library reaches target audiences, and adapting outreach strategies to include new dissemination channels and events.
- **Data integrity:** issuing annual confirmation requests to submitters to ensure that entries remain accurate and representative, preventing the accumulation of outdated or abandoned projects.

In addition to academic integration, XR4Europe will disseminate and promote the Library within the Virtual Worlds Partnership Association, subject to agreement with its leadership. This will allow members from industry and research to contribute their works. The Library will also be presented at major European XR events where XR4Europe participates, such as United XR, Nordic VR Forum, Immersive Tech Week, and Festival of the Future, with selected projects showcased as exemplars of ethical practice.

Finally, XR4Europe foresees the potential expansion of the Library's scope to include commercial projects alongside academic and non-commercial works. This would increase its relevance by

highlighting both grassroots initiatives and market-leading applications, providing benchmarks for ethical and human-centred design across the XR industry.

KPI: Annual review of scope and criteria; at least one university partnership integrated by 2026; one dedicated Library workshop held each year at a major European XR event.

1.5 Continuity of the Ratings Repository

The Ratings Repository is an important part of the XR4HUMAN legacy, as it provides a structured reference point for project outputs and offers a pathway for continued evaluation of ethical and human-centred practices. As part of the migration plan, the Repository will be transferred from NTUA's servers to XR4Europe's hosting environment, alongside the Experience Library. This move ensures that XR4Europe can continue to maintain the Repository as a living resource, with the authority to update linked materials and ensure that they remain accessible.

The Repository itself will not undergo significant structural changes following the migration. Its framework will remain largely as it was established during the project, preserving its consistency and usability. The main dynamic element within the Repository will be the XR Code of Conduct, which is hosted there in its living version. XR4Europe will update this document periodically as new stakeholder consultations, collaborations, and international alignments occur. This allows the Repository to remain current without requiring fundamental redesign or redevelopment.

In practice, XR4Europe will also use the Repository to publish updated project-related files, such as case studies or revisions to the ethical self-assessment form, while maintaining clear attribution to XR4HUMAN. Updates will be announced through the Forum and XR4Europe's communication channels, ensuring visibility and engagement. By positioning the Repository as the public access point for the evolving Code of Conduct and related resources, XR4Europe reinforces its value as a practical, enduring tool for the European XR ecosystem.

KPI: Migration of Repository to XR4Europe servers by January 2026; updates to linked Code of Conduct hosted as a living document.

1.6 Sustainability of the Interoperability Guide

The Interoperability Guide will remain part of the XR4HUMAN website hosted by NTUA, preserved in its final form as developed within the project. Unlike the Experience Library or the Code of Conduct, the Guide does not require continuous updates or interactive features to retain its usefulness. Instead, it will function as an informative and interactive web asset for researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders interested in the state of XR interoperability at the conclusion of the project.

NTUA will maintain the Guide as part of its long-term commitment to the XR4HUMAN website, ensuring that it remains publicly available for at least five years after the project's completion. While the Guide itself will not evolve structurally, its visibility and relevance will be maintained through XR4Europe's ongoing engagement with international standards organisations such as the Metaverse Standards Forum, Khronos Group, and other global working groups. In this way, the Guide will be complemented by XR4Europe's active participation in contemporary debates and standardisation initiatives, which will ensure that the knowledge captured within it remains situated within broader European and international efforts.

XR4Europe will also highlight the Guide in conferences and workshops on standards and interoperability, presenting it as a European contribution to a fast-changing global discourse. The Guide will continue to serve as a foundation upon which XR4Europe builds its contributions to new standardisation efforts, ensuring that XR4HUMAN's work remains embedded in future developments.

KPI: Continued hosting of the Interoperability Guide by NTUA for at least five years; annual promotion of the Guide through XR4Europe's standards-related activities.

2 Risk Assessment and Mitigation

The sustainability of XR4HUMAN outputs requires addressing risks related to resources, engagement, adoption, technology, and alignment. Financial risk will be jointly managed by XR4Europe and NTUA, who commit to covering the costs of hosting and maintaining the project’s digital legacy, including the XR4HUMAN website, Forum, Arrival.Space webspace, and project URLs. XR4Europe will additionally cover Discourse hosting and the migration of dynamic assets such as the Experience Library and Ratings Repository.

Engagement risk will be mitigated through a multi-pronged approach. XR4Europe will organise semesterly Forum workshops to sustain dialogue and annual showcases of the Experience Library at major conferences. Outreach will also target new Horizon Europe projects and universities offering XR and virtual worlds training or degree programmes. Early discussions with institutions such as St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences and Avans University of Applied Sciences illustrate the potential for embedding the Experience Library and the Code of Conduct into teaching curricula. At the same time, outreach will extend to the forthcoming Virtual Worlds Skills Academy, a Digital Europe initiative that will integrate XR and virtual world skills training at scale, providing a natural channel for long-term adoption of XR4HUMAN’s Code of Conduct and contribution to its Experience Library.

Adoption risk for the Code of Conduct will be addressed through envisioned webinars with the Virtual Worlds Partnership Association, timed to coincide with project kick-off cycles, and through periodic updates that include sector-specific adaptations. Technological risks are minimised by reliance on managed hosting and widely supported platforms, with flexibility to migrate if required. Fragmentation risks will be mitigated by collaborating with XRSI Europe and the XR Guild, ensuring XR4HUMAN outputs complement other ethical initiatives rather than compete with them.

Legacy Area	Lead Responsibility	Main Post-Project Actions	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Target Timeline
Experience Library	XR4Europe	Migrate and host on XR4Europe servers; maintain public access; integrate with university curricula and the Virtual Worlds Skills Academy; conduct annual review and evaluation cycle; present annually at major XR events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migration completed by Jan 2026 • ≥ 1 university partnership by end of 2026 • Annual review of Library • One annual showcase/workshop 	2026 onward
Ratings Repository & Code of Conduct	XR4Europe	Host as living repository for evolving Code of Conduct; update following consultations and EU regulatory developments; disseminate through Virtual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository migration by Jan 2026 • ≥ 2 dissemination webinars per year • Annual update of Code content 	2026 – 2028

Legacy Area	Lead Responsibility	Main Post-Project Actions	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Target Timeline
		Worlds Partnership webinars and conferences.		
XR4HUMAN Forum	XR4Europe	Maintain Discourse-hosted Forum for minimum 3 years; organise semesterly workshops; engage new Horizon Europe projects and partner initiatives (XRSI Europe, XR Guild).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biannual activity evaluation • Continuous outreach to HEU projects 	2025 - 2028
XR4HUMAN Website & Interoperability Guide	NTUA	Preserve XR4HUMAN web domain and static resources; maintain Interoperability Guide in final form; ensure long-term accessibility (≥ 5 years).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website and Guide accessible through 2030 • Annual visibility check and technical maintenance 	2025 - 2030
Alignment & Outreach Activities	XR4Europe (with partners)	Collaborate with Virtual Worlds Partnership, Virtual Worlds Skills Academy, and international standards bodies (Metaverse Standards Forum, Khronos, IEEE, ITU); promote XR4HUMAN at conferences and working groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in ≥ 3 standards group activities/year • 1 joint activity / year with the Partnership or Skills Academy • Representation at ≥ 1 European XR events annually 	2025 - 2028
Financial & Technical Sustainability	XR4Europe & NTUA	Jointly manage hosting, maintenance, and renewal costs for Forum, website, URLs, and Arrival.Space environment; secure new EU or partner funding when available.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous uptime of all web assets • Annual cost review and joint budget update 	2025 - 2028